

Assessing Antiviral Mechanisms of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine, N-acetylcysteine and Acetylsalicylic acid on SARS-CoV-2

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Abstract

Objective: The potential antiviral activity of FDA-approved 3 compounds (N-acetyl-D-glucosamine; GlcNAc, N-acetylcysteine; NAC, and Acetylsalicylic acid; ASA) against SARS-CoV-2 was investigated.

Materials and Methods: Molecular docking analysis of these compounds as ligands with the main 22 viral proteins was made to predict their possible interaction.

Results: All molecules showed interactions with the viral proteins; the mean binding scores for GlcNAc and ASA were very close (-6.81 kcal/mol and -6.31 kcal/mol, respectively), while NAC designated the lowest value (-4.69 kcal/mol). GlcNAc showed the highest binding energy of -8.80 kcal/mol against both the target proteins RdRp-RTP site (7BV2) and Helicase-ANP binding site (7NN0).

Conclusion: Since these 22 proteins, including main protease (Mpro) and Papain-like protease (PLpro), are responsible for replication and various pathogenesis processes, it could be concluded that these FDA-approved commercially available compounds have antiviral properties against SARS-CoV-2, which should be confirmed with further *in vivo* and clinical trials.

Keywords; bioinformatics, ligand, molecular docking, nCoV, repurposing, SARS-CoV-2

Graphical abstract

1. INTRODUCTION

Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) represents a novel strain of coronavirus that has precipitated a global pandemic characterized by acute respiratory illness in humans (Tay et al., 2020; van Eijk et al., 2021). This emergence follows previous outbreaks of coronaviruses, namely Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV), both of which have contributed to the broader understanding of coronavirus-related diseases (Zhou et al., 2020). Since the emergence of COVID-19, more than 700 million individuals have been reported to have tested positive for the virus, and over 7 million people have passed away due to the disease (according to <https://covid19.WHO.int/>). SARS-CoV-2 possesses all the characteristic structural components of other coronaviruses (Liang et al., 2020). Nonetheless, when SARS-CoV was compared with SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV-2 exhibited specific structural alterations that increased its transmissibility (Malone et al., 2022).

Similar to SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 gains entry into host cells by binding to its primary functional receptor, angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), a receptor that is ubiquitously expressed on epithelial and endothelial cells across multiple tissues and organs (Hashimoto et al., 2012; Varga et al., 2020). The widespread distribution of ACE2 in various tissues, coupled with the effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the receptor's physiological functions, plays a significant role in shaping the clinical manifestations of the disease (Bourgonje et al., 2020; Yan et al., 2020).

COVID-19 causes a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations, ranging from mild symptoms, including dry cough, fever, and sore throat, to more severe pathological conditions such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), multi-organ failure (MOF), and, in some cases, fatality. The severity of the disease is closely associated with the host's immune response to the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Huang et al., 2020; Tay et al., 2020).

A robust immune response is essential for eliminating the virus, while a dysfunctional response results in viral persistence and an overproduction of inflammatory mediators, leading to a cytokine storm and progression of the disease.

Different stages of COVID-19 should be treated with customized approaches that consider the pathogenic traits of SARS-CoV-2. In the initial phase of the illness, it is essential to block viral entry and replication, while in the later phase characterized by significant inflammation, strategies to manage or reduce the inflammatory response should be implemented (Kim et al., 2021; Schurink et al., 2020).

Vaccination represents a primary and highly effective strategy for preventing SARS-CoV-2 infection and mitigating the severity of the disease. Some international pharmaceutical companies have developed various mRNA-based vaccines derived from the spike protein of the virus during the pandemic (Bettini and Locci, 2021). Although these vaccines have been approved for governmental vaccination programmes in many countries (Yadav et al. 2023), there are some concerns about their side effects, and their long-term effects are unknown (Yasmin et al. 2023). Therefore, new alternative SARS-CoV-2 treatment methods are also necessary.

Repurposing FDA approved compound is one of the ways to shorten the developing process for a new treatment. Also, another factor is to determine the target proteins that have key roles in replication machinery of virus. Recent techniques such as molecular docking simulations have improved by increase in computational processing power. These techniques let us examine the molecular aspects of proteins and protein–ligand interactions for new drug candidates or repurposing recent drugs (Baysal and Silme, 2021).

In this study, selected SARS-CoV-2 proteins responsible for replication cycle and other cellular activities were investigated for their interactions with 3 FDA approved compounds; N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (GlcNAc), N-acetylcysteine (NAC), and Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA).

This study aims to determine the difference in binding score within selected proteins and compounds, to enhance our understanding of potential therapeutic approaches for the treatment and management of diseases. In particular, it aims to inform the development of novel treatment strategies for future public health challenges arising from coronavirus outbreaks.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To explore the interaction of GlcNAc, NAC, and ASA with the selected proteins of the SARS-CoV-2, molecular docking simulations were performed utilizing the COVID-19 Docking Server 2.0 (<https://ncovdock2.schanglab.org.cn>, Liu et al., 2023). This novel docking server called nCoVDock2 was developed by Liu et al. (2023) to predict the binding modes between the targeted SARS-CoV-2 proteins and their possible ligands. For the docking of small molecules, AutoDock Vina (ver. 1.2.0) was integrated as the docking engine (Eberhardt et al. 2021; Trott and Olson, 2010). Also, Open Babel was utilized for converting formats or generating 3D coordinates for the files that were uploaded (O'Boyle et al., 2011). The docking box is specified by the center of the native ligand coordinates and has dimensions of 30 Å × 30 Å × 30 Å to encompass all the residues within the cavity. Homology-modeled structures are characterized based on the details of active sites or binding sites found in their homologs from SARS-CoV. The MGLTools software was utilized to incorporate hydrogens and generate pdbqt files for both proteins and ligands. All parameters were configured to their default settings, and for this study the exhaustiveness value option was set to 16. All the proteins shown in Table 1 were utilized for the docking analysis in this server. The 3D sdf ligand files for the selected molecules were obtained from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>; NCBI, 2025) and subsequently uploaded to the nCoVDock2 server. The protein-ligand interactions were visualized by nCoVDock2 server. Autodock Vina binding affinity score was described as score value (SV) and also a machine learning scoring function described as RF-Score was used to evaluate the binding affinities for small molecules (Liu et al., 2023).

3. RESULTS

Molecular docking simulations conducted to assess the binding affinities of GlcNAc, NAC, and ASA with the specific protein sites of SARS-CoV-2, showed all the compounds have strong interactions with the proteins, which show their potential interferences with the life cycle of SARS-CoV-2 (Table 1; Sup. Data 1).

The docking results of all compounds with selected proteins according to expressed binding score values (kcal/mol) and RF score values are presented in Table 1. These results correspond to the highest-ranked docking poses, representing the most optimal models of the studied protein–ligand complexes. The highest bindings were predicted by the lower score values that demonstrated a significant strength of interactions between ligands and proteins.

Table 1. SARS-CoV-2 protein docking results of selected molecules. SV; score value, RF SV; RF score value.

Protein	GlcNAc		NAC		ASA		
	SV (kcal/mol)	RF SV (pKd)	SV (kcal/mol)	RF SV (pKd)	SV (kcal/mol)	RF SV (pKd)	
1	Nsp3-macrodomein (5RSF)	-6.40	4.33	-4.30	4.42	-6.40	4.56
2	Nsp3-ADP ribose phosphatase (6W6Y)	-6.10	4.15	-4.20	4.48	-6.00	4.53
3	Nsp3-MES site (6W6Y)	-7.00	4.54	-5.00	4.38	-6.40	4.61
4	PLpro-WT (7RZC)	-7.40	4.95	-4.70	4.65	-6.90	4.65
5	PLpro-C111S (7SQE)	-7.40	4.97	-4.80	4.68	-6.70	4.44
6	Mpro-WT (7SI9)	-6.30	4.55	-4.70	4.44	-5.80	4.40
7	Nsp9-FR6 bound (7KRI)	-5.70	4.60	-3.90	4.23	-5.50	4.60
8	Nsp9-oridonin bound (7N3K)	-6.20	4.40	-4.00	4.38	-5.70	4.45
9	Nsp10-nsp10-14 (7ORR)	-6.20	4.66	-4.00	4.21	-5.10	4.38
10	Nsp10-nsp10-16 (7ORU)	-5.90	4.42	-5.00	4.41	-5.60	4.64
11	RdRp-RTP site (7BV2)	-8.80	5.21	-5.60	5.74	-7.20	4.76
12	RdRp-RNA site (7D4F)	-6.40	4.80	-4.40	4.14	-5.90	4.71
13	Helicase-ANP binding site (7NN0)	-8.80	5.03	-5.70	5.82	-6.40	4.70
14	Helicase-fragment binding site (5RML)	-7.20	5.45	-5.70	5.96	-6.60	4.86
15	Nsp10-14-chapso site (7N0D)	-6.80	4.77	-4.50	4.72	-6.40	4.39
16	Nsp10-14-ExoN (7N0D)	-6.60	4.73	-4.10	4.39	-6.30	4.82
17	Nsp10-14-N7-MTase (7N0D)	-6.80	4.85	-4.60	4.80	-6.40	4.52
18	Nsp15-WT (7K1L)	-6.40	4.29	-4.80	4.38	-6.00	4.41
19	Nsp10-16-MGP site (6WVN)	-7.10	4.50	-4.90	4.32	-7.10	4.90
20	Nsp10-16-SAM site (6W4H)	-7.10	4.55	-4.80	4.59	-7.10	4.90
21	Nsp10-16-GTA site (6WVN)	-7.10	4.50	-5.00	4.37	-7.10	4.89
22	N protein-NCB site (MODEL)	-6.30	4.22	-4.60	4.24	-6.40	4.41
Mean value	-6.81	4.65	-4.69	4.62	-6.31	4.61	

The results in Table 1 show that all the molecules have interactions with Sars-CoV-2 proteins at various levels (thus with different scores). Score mean values from highest to lowest are -6.81 kcal/mol (GlcNAc), -6.31 kcal/mol (ASA), and -4.69 kcal/mol (NAC). All the viral proteins in Table 1 have key roles in replication and pathogenesis cycle, but main protease (Mpro) was selected in Figure 1 to show its interaction with selected compounds due to its indispensable role in viral replication and have been recognized as key targets for preventing and treating coronavirus causing infectious diseases (Hu et al., 2022). As shown in Table 1, the highest interaction score was recorded for GlcNAc (-6.30 kcal/mol) which indicates its inhibitory potential on this protein (Sup. Data 1).

Furthermore, Papain-like protease (PLpro) represents a compelling antiviral target due to its essential role in the replication of coronaviruses (Varghese et al., 2025). PLpro has acquired an enhanced ability to cleave the ubiquitin-like interferon-stimulated gene 15 (ISG15) protein, due to genomic alterations in SARS-CoV-2, thereby facilitating the virus's evasion of the host innate immune response. Notably, Table 1 shows that PLpro enzymes from wild type (7RZC) and C111S mutant (7SQE) viruses have the same score (-7.40 kcal/mol) for their interaction with GlcNAc, which is higher than the other two compounds, indicating its antiviral potential.

Figure 1. Structural docking simulations of Mpro and selected compounds; a) GlcNAc, b) NAC, and c) ASA. The selected compounds are indicated in purple colour.

4. DISCUSSION

The SARS-CoV-2 virus exhibits a spherical morphology, with a diameter ranging from approximately 65 to 125 nm. The spike (S) protein, located on the viral surface, imparts the characteristic crown-like ("corona") appearance, from which the virus derives its name (Liang et al., 2020; van Eijk et al., 2021). Coronaviruses are characterized by having the largest single-stranded, positive-sense RNA genome, with a length ranging between 26 and 32 kilobases (Malone et al., 2022; V'Kovski et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020).

Approximately two-thirds of the coronaviral genome consists of genes that encode non-structural proteins, including RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp), proteases, and helicase, all of which are critical for viral replication. The 3' end of the genome encodes the four major structural proteins of the coronavirus virion: the spike (S), membrane (M), envelope (E), and nucleocapsid (N) proteins (Figure 2; Malone et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020). Several viral proteins of Coronaviruses manipulate the immune response of the host (Minkoff and tenOever, 2023; Wong and Perlman, 2022).

Figure 2. Genomic distribution of SARS-Cov-2 genes (Source: BioRender).

Although the global pandemic of SARS-CoV-2 has faded, due to possibility of a new outbreak a continued focus is necessary. The complex pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 demands multifaceted strategies to effectively manage the COVID-19 pandemic, wherein modulating the inflammatory response is of equal importance to directly targeting the virus itself. In this perspective, repurposing recent drugs provide us a primary advantage for developing new treatments against SARS-CoV-2.

Complementary with this strategy, the previous studies have described anti-inflammatory activities and immune response modulating properties of GlcNAc on SARS-CoV-2, which confirms results of the recent study (Baysal et al., 2021a; 2021b; Hassan, 2021; Qi et al., 2023). Also, the studies on ASA showed its inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2 replication cycle (Geiger et al., 2022), which makes it a promising drug candidate for the SARS-CoV-2 treatments (Bianconi et al., 2020; Cacciapuoti and Cacciapuoti, 2021; Mazik, 2022; Rizk et al., 2021). Although the mean value of NAC was found to be less than other values of the compounds in this study (Table 1), particularly many studies have shown anti-viral property of NAC on SARS-CoV-2 (Avdeev et al., 2022; Faverio et al., 2021; Izquierdo-Alonso et al., 2022; Wong et al., 2021). From these results, it could be concluded that both GlcNAc and ASA could response better in SARS-CoV-2 treatments since their mean value is higher than NAC (Table

1). Though there are limited studies on these compounds, more research on their inhibitory potential on SARS-CoV-2 *in vivo* and clinical trials is necessary.

It is noteworthy that, although these three compounds do not need any prescription, only one of them has a long pharmaceutical history; acetylsalicylic acid, which is better known for more than 125 years under its trade name of Aspirin. The antiviral effects of this compound have been confirmed with testing on both RNA and DNA viruses with several *in vitro* and experimental *in vivo* studies (Werz et al., 2024). Also, low-cost production of Aspirin makes it a promising drug candidate for further anti-SARS-CoV-2 studies.

Figure 3. Structural comparison of selected molecules; a) GlcNAc, b) NAC, and c) ASA.

As depicted in Figure 3, the molecular structure of these compounds are different, therefore their mode of action is expected to be various in many metabolic pathways. The immunomodulatory properties of these compounds on SARS-CoV-2 are also needed to be investigated in further studies.

The emergence of new mutated variants such as Omicron variant confirms the unpredictable nature of the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasizing the need for repurposing new drugs with ongoing research, adaptability, and global collaboration. The COVID-19 Docking Server 2.0 has a great potential as an integrated bioinformatics tool in research for SARS-CoV-2 protein ligand interactions (Liu et al., 2023). The bioinformatics analysis infrastructure available here can guide us in developing treatment methods rapidly, as it contains common or similar proteins across all coronavirus variants.

5. CONCLUSION

This study identified the interaction of 3 FDA approved commercially available and widely used compounds; GlcNAc, NAC, and ASA acid with 22 main proteins of SARS-CoV-2, which have major roles related to replication and various pathogenesis processes. All the compounds found to have interaction with these 22 proteins. Mean values of interactions indicated that GlcNAc (-6.81 kcal/mol) and ASA (-6.31 kcal/mol) have similar results but NAC (-4.69 kcal/mol) was found to have the lowest value. Due to high evolution property of the SARS-CoV-2, new variants could emerge in near future. These compounds could be used in SARS-CoV-2 treatments after the confirmation of the results *in vivo* and clinical trials.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

RSS: conceptualization, resources, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

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